

Synthesis and spectroscopic studies of cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes with N-donor (N₄) macrocyclic ligand (DSLFL)

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Abstract : Complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} containing a tetradentate macrocyclic nitrogen ligand have been prepared via template reaction of 2,3-pentanedione, *m*-phenylenediamine and transition metal ions. The complexes have been characterized on the basis of elemental analysis, molar conductance measurements, magnetic susceptibility measurements, infrared, EPR and UV-Visible electronic absorption spectral studies.

Keywords : Cobalt(II), nickel(II), copper(II), macrocyclic ligand, spectral studies.

Introduction

The tetra-aza macrocyclic ligands and their metal complexes have attracted growing interest among the coordination chemists¹. Interest in multidentate acyclic/macrocyclic compounds is continuously increasing because of their unique properties and use in the synthesis of polynuclear metal complexes which mimic metalloproteins, magnetically concentrated systems, molecules exhibiting catalytic activity and optically induced intrasystem charge-transfer transitions². Curtis and coworkers^{1,2} were first to report the synthesis of some macrocyclic ligands, especially of hexamethyltetraazacyclotetradeca-tetraene. Since then, several macrocyclic ligands such as cyclam³, cyclen², aminobenzaldehyde trimers and tetramers⁴⁻⁷ have been reported.

In this paper we report the synthesis and characterization of cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) complexes with 1,4,10,13-tetraaza-2,12-diethyl-3,11-dimethyl-tricyclo[13,3,1.1⁵⁻⁹]-1,3,5,7,9(20),10,12,14(19),15,17-decane (DSLFL) macrocyclic ligand (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Two possible isomeric form of the ligand (DSLFL).

Results and discussion

Two isomers are possible i.e. 2,12-diethyl-3,11-dimethyl- or 2,11-diethyl-3,12-dimethyl-isomers for the ligand (DSLFL). For the analysis of ligand, thin layer chromatography (TLC) has been performed and it has been found that the ligand is not a mixture of two isomeric forms. However, it is quite difficult to say that whether the ligand is either the 2,12-diethyl-3,11-dimethyl- or 2,11-diethyl-3,12-dimethyl-isomer without X-ray crystallography. Since the complexes were prepared by the template condensation reaction method, the complexes may have again either 2,12-diethyl-3,11-dimethyl- or 2,11-diethyl-3,12-dimethyl-structure or a mixture of these two isomers. However the possibility of a mixture is ruled out by performing thin layer chromatography (TLC). The positions of both methyl and ethyl groups are in the different reported positions, although, this will not affect the behavior of the ligand and the geometry of the complexes.

On the basis of elemental analyses data (Table 1), the general compositions M(DSLFL)X₂ have been suggested for the complexes [DSLFL = 1,4,10,13-tetraaza-2,12-diethyl-3,11-dimethyl-tricyclo[13,3,1.1⁵⁻⁹]-1,3,5,7,9(20),10,12,14(19),15,17-decane; M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}; X = Cl⁻, NO₃⁻, ½SO₄²⁻ for Cu^{II} and X = SCN⁻, ½SO₄²⁻, Cl⁻, NO₃⁻ for Co^{II} and Ni^{II}, sulphato complex of Ni^{II} could not be synthesized due to poor yield. Molar conductance measurements of all the complexes, in DMSO solutions lie in the range 9.86–14.82 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ in-

Table 1. Elemental analyses, colour, yield, molar conductance and composition of the complexes

Sr. no.	Complex	Colour	Yield (%)	Molar conduc. ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	Analysis (%) : Calcd. (Found)			
					M	C	H	N
1.	[Co(DSLF)Cl ₂]	Black	84	10.98	12.42	55.76	4.64	11.86
	CoC ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₄ Cl ₂				(12.46)	(55.72)	(4.72)	(11.81)
2.	[Co(DSLF)(NCS) ₂]	Black	88	10.78	11.38	55.56	4.68	16.21
	CoC ₂₄ H ₂₄ N ₆ S ₂				(11.38)	(55.48)	(4.62)	(16.33)
3.	[Co(DSLF)(NO ₃) ₂]	Brown	76	201.34	11.21	50.15	4.24	15.98
	CoC ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₆ O ₆				(11.24)	(50.18)	(4.29)	(16.05)
4.	[Co(DSLF)SO ₄]	Violet	82	9.86	11.82	52.94	4.42	11.24
	CoC ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₄ SO ₄				(11.87)	(52.99)	(4.38)	(11.27)
5.	[Ni(DSLF)Cl ₂]	Green	72	14.82	12.36	55.72	5.14	11.81
	NiC ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₄ Cl ₂				(12.38)	(55.84)	(5.21)	(11.92)
6.	[Ni(DSLF)(NCS) ₂]	Dark grey	75	13.28	11.32	55.48	4.62	16.15
	NiC ₂₄ H ₂₄ N ₆ S ₂				(11.35)	(55.42)	(4.66)	(16.23)
7.	[Ni(DSLF)(NO ₃) ₂]	Light green	87	12.24	11.15	50.14	4.56	15.92
	NiC ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₆ O ₆				(11.22)	(50.21)	(4.52)	(15.86)
8.	[Cu(DSLF)Cl ₂]	Violet	84	13.39	13.26	55.17	5.05	11.62
	CuC ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₄ Cl ₂				(13.34)	(55.13)	(5.02)	(11.68)
9.	[Cu(DSLF)(NO ₃) ₂]	Black	76	12.38	11.92	49.74	4.62	15.74
	CuC ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₆ O ₆				(11.96)	(49.86)	(4.64)	(15.82)
10.	[Cu(DSLF)SO ₄]	Dark green	82	12.84	12.62	52.37	4.84	11.16
	CuC ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₄ SO ₄				(12.68)	(52.44)	(4.89)	(11.11)

dicating that the complexes are non-electrolyte in nature⁸ and thus may be formulated as [M(DSLF)X₂]. On the other hand, complex Co(DSLF)(NO₃)₂ shows molar conductance value corresponding to 1 : 2 electrolyte^{9,10} i.e. 201.34 S cm² mol⁻¹, indicating that the nitrate group are ionic in nature and may be formulated as [Co(DSLF)](NO₃)₂.

The magnetic moment values of the nickel(II), cobalt(II) and copper(II) complexes are presented in Table 2. The Co^{II} complexes show magnetic moments in the range of 4.62 to 5.04 B.M., while Ni^{II} complexes show magnetic moments in the range of 3.08 to 3.16 B.M. at room temperature. The magnetic moments of Cu^{II} complexes lie in the range of 1.92 to 2.02 B.M., corresponding to one unpaired electron. The values are in tune with a high-spin configuration and show the presence of an octahedral environment around the Ni^{II} and Co^{II} ion except the complex [Co(DSLF)(NO₃)₂] and [Co(DSLF)SO₄] which possess tetrahedral and trigonal bipyramidal geometry¹¹⁻¹⁴. All the copper complexes may be considered to have tetragonal geometry except the sulphato complex which possesses square-pyramidal geometry around the Cu²⁺ ion and the anions occupied the axial positions. The possible geometry of the complexes was deduced from IR,

UV-Visible electronic and EPR spectral studies¹⁵⁻¹⁸.

IR spectra of the complexes :

The IR spectra of the 2,3-pentanedione and diamines show bands at 1740 cm⁻¹ and at 3300 and 3205 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the free carbonyl and free amino group respectively. The appearance of a new strong absorption band in complexes lie in the range 1620–1660 cm⁻¹ attributable to the characteristic stretching frequencies of the imino linkage¹⁹ $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ and the absence of stretching and deformation frequencies of the amino and the carbonyl groups in the IR spectra of these macrocyclic complexes, provide strong evidence for the presence of cyclic product. An important feature is the appearance of a new medium intensity band at 405–475 cm⁻¹, attributed to $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{N}}$ which provide strong evidence for the involvement of nitrogen in coordination^{15,19}.

Bands due to anions :

The IR spectrum of the thiocyanato complex shows a number of characteristic peaks. Absorptions at 2086–2089, 852–855 and 410–416 cm⁻¹ could be assigned to $\nu_{\text{N}=\text{C}}$, $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{S}}$ and ν_{NCS} bending vibrations, respectively. The positions of the bands are in favour of monodentate co-

Table 2. Electronic spectral bands (cm⁻¹) and magnetic moments (B.M.)

Complex	μ_{eff}^b (B.M.)	$\nu_1-\lambda_{\text{max}}^a$ (cm ⁻¹) ($\epsilon = \text{L mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$) Assigned transition	$\nu_2-\lambda_{\text{max}}^a$ (cm ⁻¹) ($\epsilon = \text{L mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$) Assigned transition	$\nu_3-\lambda_{\text{max}}^a$ (cm ⁻¹) ($\epsilon = \text{L mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$) Assigned transition
[Co(DSLF)Cl ₂]	5.02	8110 (52)	15244 (73)	20900 (97)
CoC ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₄ Cl ₂		${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$	${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$	${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$
[Co(DSLF)(NCS) ₂]	5.04	8700 (58)	14892 (78)	23041 (104)
CoC ₂₄ H ₂₄ N ₆ S ₂		${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$	${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$	${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$
[Co(DSLF)(NO ₃) ₂]	4.62	5600 (28)	14620 (216)	22523
CoC ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₆ O ₆		${}^4A_2(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_1(F)$	${}^4A_2(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_1(P)$	Charge transfer band
[Co(DSLF)SO ₄]	4.92	5650 (42)	12650 (83)	15900 (96)
CoC ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₄ SO ₄		${}^4A'_2(F) \rightarrow {}^4E''(F)$	${}^4A'_2(F) \rightarrow {}^4E'(F)$	${}^4A'_2(F) \rightarrow {}^4A'_2(P)$
[Ni(DSLF)Cl ₂]	3.16	9870 (33)	15800 (62)	24520 (124)
NiC ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₄ Cl ₂		${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$	${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$	${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$
[Ni(DSLF)(NCS) ₂]	3.08	9870 (29)	17600 (81)	23740 (122)
NiC ₂₄ H ₂₄ N ₆ S ₂		${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$	${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$	${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$
[Ni(DSLF)(NO ₃) ₂]	3.12	9725 (26)	16650 (74)	22950 (118)
NiC ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₆ O ₆		${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$	${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$	${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$
[Cu(DSLF)Cl ₂]	2.02	15873 (73)	20450 (105)	22108 (154)
CuC ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₄ Cl ₂		${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$	${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$	${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$
[Cu(DSLF)(NO ₃) ₂]	1.94	12077 (65)	19600 (99)	22554 (162)
CuC ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₆ O ₆		${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$	${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$	${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$
[Cu(DSLF)SO ₄]	1.92	10194 (30)	14354 (52)	22400 (81)
CuC ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₄ SO ₄				

^aIn DMSO, ^bat room temperature.

ordination through the N atom of the -SCN group¹⁹. The IR spectra of the Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} nitrate complexes exhibit bands in the region 1228–1232, 1018–1024 and 860–866 cm⁻¹, which are consistent with the monodentate coordination of this group. While Co(DSLF)(NO₃)₂ complex exhibits a sharp band at 1385 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the uncoordinated nitrate group. The IR spectra of the sulphato complex of Co^{II} and Cu^{II} shows bands at 1136–1140 and 1054–1062 cm⁻¹, which indicate that the sulphate ion is coordinated to the metal ion unidentately.

Electronic spectra :

Cobalt(II) complexes :

The electronic spectra of chloro and thiocyanato complexes reported here show bands in the ranges 8110–8700 (52–58 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹), 14862–15244 (73–78 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) and 20900–23041 cm⁻¹ (97–104 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) (Table 2) characteristic to an octahedral geometry^{20–22} (Fig. 2 and Fig. 3). The bands may be assigned to ${}^4T_{1g}({}^4F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}({}^4F)$ ν_1 , ${}^4T_{1g}({}^4F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}({}^4F)$ ν_2 and ${}^4T_{1g}({}^4F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}({}^4F)$, ν_3 transitions respectively.

Fig. 2. Electronic spectra of the complexes, (A) = [Co(DSLF)Cl₂], (B) = [Ni(DSLF)Cl₂] and (C) = [Cu(DSLF)Cl₂].

Fig. 3. [M = Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}, where X = Cl⁻, NO₃⁻, SCN⁻] [and for Co^{II}, X = Cl⁻, SCN⁻].

The electronic spectra of tetrahedral cobalt(II) complexes do not much differ from octahedral complexes. Since, in both tetrahedral and octahedral cases, Co^{II} absorbs around 8000 and 17000 cm⁻¹ regions, so these two geometries may not be differentiated by these absorptions. However, in tetrahedral case a third band is expected to appear in the near IR region (5000 cm⁻¹) which might not be present in octahedral complexes. The complex under study shows electronic spectral bands at 5600 (28 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹), 14620 (216 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) and 22523 cm⁻¹ (Table 2) corresponding to the tetrahedral geometry³ (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Suggested structure of cobalt(II) nitrate complex.

The electronic spectrum of the sulphato complex displays four bands at 5650 (42 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) (ν_1), 12658 (83 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) (ν_2), 15900 (96 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) (ν_3)

and 21231 cm⁻¹ (158 L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹) (ν_4) (Table 2), corresponding to the trigonal-bipyramidal geometry (Lever 1968). These bands may be assigned to $^4A'_2(F) \rightarrow ^4E''(F)$ (ν_1), $^4A'_2(F) \rightarrow ^4E'(F)$ (ν_2), $^4A'_2(F) \rightarrow ^4A'_2(P)$ (ν_3) and $^4A'_2(F) \rightarrow ^4E''(P)$ (ν_4) transitions respectively, suggesting five-coordinated trigonal-bipyramidal geometry¹⁷ (Fig. 5). Trigonal-bipyramidal geometry may have either D_{3h} or C_{3v} symmetry. If the symmetry is D_{3h} , then splitting would be observed whereas no such splitting would be observed if the symmetry is C_{3v} . In the complex under study, no splitting in the ν_1 absorption band is observed, therefore, C_{3v} symmetry may be assigned for the complex under study²³.

Fig. 5. Suggested structure for cobalt(II) and copper(II) sulphato complex.

The spectral parameters ν_2/ν_1 , Dq/B , B and β values were calculated and have been found²² as 2.72, 0.44, 684 cm⁻¹ and 0.61, respectively. The lowering in the B value from the free ion value of cobalt(II) (1120 cm⁻¹) suggests 39 to 41% covalent nature in bonding. These values are very close to octahedral and tetrahedral geometry around the cobalt(II) in the complexes under study (Fig. 6).

The EPR spectra of the complexes under study were recorded at liquid nitrogen temperature because the rapid

Fig. 6. Mass spectrum of the cobalt(II) chloride complex.

relaxation of Co^{II} broadened the lines at higher temperatures. The values of g_{\parallel} and g_{\perp} are reported in Table 4 and lies in the range, $g_{\parallel} = 3.948\text{--}5.354$, $g_{\perp} = 1.963\text{--}2.617$. The large deviations of the g -values from the spin-only value ($g = 2.0023$) is due to the large angular momentum contribution.

Nickel(II) complexes :

The electronic spectra reported here show bands in the range 9725–9870 ($26\text{--}33 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) (ν_1), 15800–17600 ($62\text{--}81 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) (ν_2) and 22950–24520 cm^{-1} ($118\text{--}124 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) (ν_3) (Table 2) characteristic to an octahedral geometry^{23,24} (Fig. 3) and thus may be assigned as ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ ν_1 , ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ ν_2 and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ ν_3 respectively. Assignment of third $d\text{--}d$ transition band 22950–24520 cm^{-1} ($118\text{--}124 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) (ν_3) is very difficult and thus, it is considered as a charge transfer band.

Various ligand field parameters (Dq , B , β) for the complexes have been calculated and are reported in Table 3. The nephelauxetic parameter β is obtained by using the relation : $\beta = B_{(\text{complex})}/B_{(\text{free ion})}$, where B is the Racah interelectronic parameter. The lowering in the B value from the free ion value of nickel(II) (1041 cm^{-1}) suggests 24–37% covalent character in the bonding. Hence it concludes that the complexes have appreciable covalent character.

Table 3. Ligand field parameters of the complexes

Complex	Dq (cm^{-1})	B (cm^{-1})	β	LFSE (kJ mol^{-1})
[Co(DSLF)Cl ₂]	949	989	0.88	90.71
[Co(DSLF)(NCS) ₂]	1019	1061	0.90	97.42
[Co(DSLF)(NO ₃) ₂]	312	709	0.63	44.73
[Co(DSLF)SO ₄]	-	-	-	-
[Ni(DSLF)Cl ₂]	987	714	0.68	150.54
[Ni(DSLF)(NCS) ₂]	987	782	0.75	141.51
[Ni(DSLF)(NO ₃) ₂]	972	695	0.66	139.35

Copper(II) complexes :

Three spin-allowed transitions are expected, in the visible and near-IR region in the electronic spectra of

Cu^{II} complexes, but only a few complexes are known, in which such bands are resolved either by Gaussian Analyses or by Single Crystal Polarization²¹ studies. These bands have been assigned to the following transitions in order of increasing energy : ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ ($d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$), ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ ($d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{xy}$) and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ ($d_{x^2-y^2} \rightarrow d_{yz}$). The energy level sequence will depend on the amount of tetragonal distortion due to ligand-field and the Jahn-Teller effect^{24–27}.

The electronic spectra of the chloro and nitrate complexes reported here show two characteristic bands at 12077–15873 ($65\text{--}73 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) (ν_1), 19600–20450 ($99\text{--}105 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) (ν_2) and 22108–22950 cm^{-1} ($154\text{--}162 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) (ν_3) (Table 2). These bands may be assigned to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ transitions respectively. The ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ transition is usually not observed as a separate band in the tetragonal field. The splitting of the 2E_g state is a measure of the planar and the axial field. Since the planar field is constant in all the present complexes, the change in bands should be due to axial field only.

The complexes exhibit an anisotropic EPR spectra characteristic of tetragonal geometry²⁷ for copper(II). The observed g -values are reported in Table 4. Further, in an axial symmetry, the g -values are related by the expres-

Table 4. EPR spectral parameters of the complexes

Complex	Temperature	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}
[Co(DSLF)Cl ₂]	LNT	5.354	2.617
[Co(DSLF)(NCS) ₂]	LNT	4.322	2.012
[Co(DSLF)(NO ₃) ₂]	LNT	3.948	1.994
[Co(DSLF)SO ₄]	LNT	3.998	1.9932

sion $G = (g_{\parallel} - 2)/(g_{\perp} - 2)$, which measures the exchange interaction between the copper centers in polycrystalline samples, have been calculated. According to [Refs. 7–9] if $G > 4$, the exchange interaction is negligible. A value of $G < 4$, indicates considerable exchange interaction in the solid complexes. The calculated G values are presented in Table 5 and larger than 4, suggesting that there is no interaction between the copper centres.

Table 5. EPR spectral parameters of copper(II) complexes

Complex	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	g_{iso}	g_3	g_2	g_1	R	G
[Cu(DSLF)Cl ₂]	2.2755	2.0682	2.1374	-	-	-	-	4.05
[Cu(DSLF)(NO ₃) ₂]	2.2615	2.0555	2.1241	-	-	-	-	4.75
[Cu(DSLF)SO ₄]	-	-	2.2061	2.387	2.146	2.086	0.249	-

An IR spectrum of sulphato complex corresponds to monodentate nature of sulphate ion. Five-coordinated geometry is thus readily suggested for the complex under study. Two basic structures can be suggested for coordination number five, i.e. trigonal bipyramidal and square pyramidal, which are characterized by the ground states $d_{x^2-y^2}$ or d_{z^2} respectively⁷. EPR spectrum of the complex provides an excellent basis for distinguishing between these two ground states. For system with $g_3 > g_2 > g_1$ the ratio^{22,23} $(g_2 - g_1)/(g_3 - g_2)$ called the parameter R , is very useful for this purpose. If the ground state is predominantly, d_{z^2} , the value of R is greater than one. On the other hand, for the ground state predominantly $d_{x^2-y^2}$, the value of R is less than one.

EPR spectra of the sulphato complex under study shows three g -values. The values of g_1 , g_2 , g_3 and R are presented in Table 5. The calculated value of R for sulphato complex under study indicates a $d_{x^2-y^2}$ ground state, which is consistent with a square pyramidal geometry. The electronic spectrum of the complex again provided strong

Preparation of the complexes :

A hot ethanolic solution (20 mL) of the respective metal salt (0.025 mol) was mixed with a hot ethanolic solution (20 mL) of *m*-phenylenediamine (5.407 g, 0.05 mol). To this solution an ethanolic solution (20 mL) of 2,3-pantanedione (5.0 g, 0.05 mol) was added in the presence of an ethanolic solution (10 ml) of lithium hydroxide (0.42 g, 0.01 mol) with constant stirring (Fig. 7). This mixture was refluxed on water bath at $\sim 80^\circ\text{C}$ for 8 h. On cooling, a coloured complex precipitated out. It was filtered, washed with ethanol, and dried under vacuum over P_4O_{10} . The complexes were re-crystallized in ethanol, to get the complex in pure form. Although the complexes were made via the template route, but to confirm the structure of ligand, we have isolated pure ligand by removal of metal ion from few complexes. The isolated metal free ligand has been characterized by mass spectrometry. The purity of the ligand (purity : 99.05%, single highest impurity 0.33%) has also been checked by HPLC.

Fig. 7. Schematic path for the synthesis of complexes.

evidences in the good turn of square pyramidal geometry and exhibit bands at 10194 ($30 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$), 14534 ($52 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and 22400 cm^{-1} ($81 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). Thus for the $\text{Cu}(\text{DSLFF})\text{SO}_4$, a five-coordinate square pyramidal geometry may be proposed. Structures of complexes are given in Figs. 3 and 4.

Experimental

Synthesis of macrocyclic ligands often involved, multistep processes and the products are generally obtained in poor yields. The use of metal templates in the preparation of macrocyclic ligands has been well established as a simple method by which high yields of target compounds can be obtained. Therefore, a template reaction was carried out for the formation of complexes.

Physical measurements :

Spectroscopic grade DMSO was used for the spectral and molar conductance studies. The C, H and N data were obtained using a Carlo-Erba 1106 elemental analyzer and are reported in Table 1. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137 instrument as nujol mull/KBr pellets. Electronic spectra were recorded in DMSO on a Shimadzu UV mini-1240 spectrophotometer. Molar conductance was measured on an Elico conductivity bridge (Type CM 82T). Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made on a Gouy balance at room temperature, using $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as calibrant. EPR spectra of all the complexes were recorded on powder samples, at room temperature, on an E_4 -EPR spectrometer using the DPPH as the g -marker.

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